

Non-Advisory Teachers' Coping Strategies and Difficulties in Blended Learning Modality

DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.15643223

Kharl Jan M. Riolo

Teacher III, Bata Elementary School II, Philippines

<https://orcid.org/0009-0008-5312-2585>

Dr. May P. Bautista

Public School District Supervisor, Department of Education, Philippines

<https://orcid.org/0009-0007-1939-9807>

Abstract:

Blended learning, which combines traditional face-to-face instruction with online learning components, has gained significant traction in educational institutions worldwide. This study explored the coping strategies and challenges experienced by non-advisory teachers in implementing blended learning modality in one of the districts in a medium-sized schools division in Central Philippines for the School Year 2024-2025. The study employed a descriptive research design and a fully validated and reliability tested self-made questionnaire for the 56 teachers to take. The areas covered included Working Environment, Ancillary Services, and Learning Modality. The result of the study showed that the level of coping strategies of non-advisory teachers in blended learning was high and the difficulties encountered was at moderate level. The study further revealed that there was a significant difference in the level of coping strategy when respondents were grouped according to age, civil status, highest educational attainment and length of service, as well as with the difficulties they encountered. The study recommended some programs to address identified areas needing actions.

Keywords: Non-advisory teachers, coping strategies, blended learning modality, difficulties

Introduction:

Nature of the Problem

Blended learning, which blends traditional in-person instruction with online learning elements, has become increasingly popular in educational institutions across the globe. Although advisory teachers frequently play a direct role in helping students navigate this complex environment, non-advisory teachers—those who only concentrate on teaching content without ongoing student mentoring—face particular difficulties and adopt particular coping mechanisms (Fabro et al., 2023).

Blended learning, as it is currently referred to, is the blending of traditional instruction with technology. While some instructors are more comfortable offering online instruction than those with tenure, not all teachers possess sufficient proficiency in using technology, posing a challenge in blended learning setting. According to Alvarez (2020), many, if not all, of the teachers at the school where the researcher is presently assigned are having difficulty juggling the learning modality, ancillary services, and working environment. Creating lengthy Powerpoint presentations, offering online activities that would boost student engagement, and providing relevant video clips are just a few of the time-consuming transitions required when switching from in-person to online instruction.

From the study of Salmorin and Motus (2024), it was revealed that the some of the challenges encountered by teachers, with or without advisory, in blended learning modality included lack of teacher exposure and readiness in the implementation of blended learning; struggle with time management, stress from excessive workloads, slow connectivity, and unmotivated students, among others.

As a non-advisory teacher, these are some of the issues that the researcher personally encountered and these issues motivated him to conduct this study. This study aimed to identify the coping strategies and challenges of non-advisory teachers in the use of blended learning modality so that proper attention can be given to weaker areas.

Current State of Knowledge

The teaching-learning process was affected in a number of ways during the epidemic and became one of the most important factors to take into account. Throughout their teaching careers, educators faced a variety of difficulties and experiences (Klapproth et al., 2020).

Khan and Kha (2019) state that one of the challenges teachers have is correctly grading students after they have been assessed and evaluated using online platforms. Teachers in this study have been negatively impacted by the pandemic's low resources, and they are overworked and worn out from working under greater demands. Online distance learning is taking the role of some traditional classroom courses. In particular, teachers' experiences modifying lessons, instruction, and evaluations to keep students interested while upholding academic objectives without overburdening them or causing needless stress.

Although blended learning has long been the goal of the Malaysian Education Ministry in both public and private tertiary education institutions, as stated in the Malaysian Higher Education Blueprint, its popularity in the local educational landscape has only recently increased as a result of educators being compelled to temporarily implement online teaching and learning due to the global crisis, which pushed them to investigate online learning tools and platforms. As we go into the post-pandemic phase, more educators are adopting the blended learning method in their classroom instruction because they are aware of the internet resources that are useful and efficient in the given context. Numerous studies have been conducted to look into how teachers view blended learning and the difficulties they face. Nonetheless, the majority of the material now in publication concentrates on teaching and studying ESL at the secondary and university levels. There, blended learning is still not well understood, especially in the setting of elementary school. Stakeholders are unable to obtain comprehensive perspectives on blended learning, particularly in the setting of elementary level ESL classrooms, due to the dearth of literature (Rajesh, 2022).

The Philippine educational system is currently adopting the most modern blended learning strategy, which is currently in use throughout the world. The education sector is convinced that education shouldn't be compromised, despite calls for an academic halt in reaction to the coronavirus outbreak. Teachers are struggling to deal with this pandemic, especially traditional teachers. As all firms ceased operations, the economy collapsed and the world came to a halt. For example, the majority of nations closed their universities, colleges, and schools to stop the virus from spreading. The crisis had an impact on more than only the health and education sectors. At the height of the pandemic, educational institutions offered remote learning as an option. Despite the shutdown order, classes continue (Padilla, 2022).

Salmorin and Motus (2024) claim that blended learning has emerged as a viable option for students who choose to continue their education by combining in-person instruction with online or modular distance learning. In practice, it allowed the students to learn at their own pace and enhanced their learning. Blended learning proved challenging to adopt in some institutions, though, particularly for students who required assistance with their assignments and support from professors when they were struggling. As a result, teachers may still experience fatigue from creating modules, reviewing them later, and planning classes and discussions all at once. Some teachers are unable to provide modules on time because of their excessive workload in in-person classes.

In a different study, Padilla (2020) identified the difficulties and coping mechanisms faced by new instructors in Urbiztondo, Pangasinan, using the modular distance learning modality. Lack of printing materials and supplies, time commitment, power outages, parents not receiving the modules, not adhering to the schedule, late submission, unanswered/unfinished modules, unidentified answer sheets, dirty, damaged modules with torn and missing pages, academic dishonesty, and difficulty validating students' performance are the challenges faced by new teachers using the modular distance learning modality, according to the study. Furthermore, new teachers use time management techniques, maintain a positive attitude, and seek mentorship to overcome the difficulties of the modular distance learning modality. Additionally, they are better able to handle the difficulties they face since they are adaptable and flexible.

Theoretical Underpinnings

Two theories served as the foundation for this investigation: Transactional Theory for Coping Strategies by Richard Lazarus and Susan Folkman (1984) and the theory Optimal Challenges by Robert Yerkes and John D. Dodson (1908). This theory provides a framework for understanding the complex interplay between stress, appraisal, and coping among teachers who were new then to blended learning modality. The theory relates to the importance of individual differences on how teachers perceive and respond to stressors. Additionally, it highlights the dynamic and ongoing nature of stress management. This is therefore useful in understanding the coping mechanisms of non-advisory teachers as they navigate through the difficult transitioning period from the old face-to-face to now technology-ridden Blended Learning Modality.

Whereas, the Theory of Optimal Challenges by Yerkes and Dodson (1908), this theory provides us with the understanding of the relationship between stress and task performance. It proposes that a person can reach his peak level of performance with an intermediate level of stress, or arousal. Too little or too much arousal results in poorer performance. This is also known as the inverted-U model of arousal. The theory basically tells us that having no stress at all isn't necessarily a good thing in terms of performance. For example, when your job is all about routine and nothing ever changes, boredom sets in (White, 2020).

Objectives of the Study

This study aimed to determine the level of coping strategies of non-advisory and the level of difficulties they encountered in the use of Blended Learning Modality in one of the districts in a medium sized schools division in Central Philippines for the School Year 2024-2025. Furthermore, this study sought to answer the following questions: 1) the level of coping strategies of non-advisory teachers in the use of Blended Learning Modality in terms of working environment, ancillary services, and learning modality; 2) the level of difficulties of non-advisory teachers in the use of Blended Learning Modality according to the aforementioned areas; 3) if there is a significant difference in the level of coping strategies of non-advisory teachers; 4) if there is there a significant difference in the level of difficulties of non-advisory teachers in the use of Blended Learning Modality.

Methodology:

Research Design

Descriptive design was employed in determining the level of coping strategies and the difficulties encountered by non-advisory teachers in blended learning for the School Year 2024-2025 This study's descriptive design is appropriate since it aimed to identify prevailing conditions or relationships, held beliefs and attitudes, processes and effects, and emerging trends. The design is a scientific methodology that entails monitoring and characterizing a subject's behavior without exerting any influence

Respondents

The respondents of the study were the 56 non-advisory teachers assigned in seven (7) different schools in this district for the School Year 2024-2025. The paper made use of purposive sampling to determine the sample size.

Instruments

To determine the level of coping strategies of non-advisory and the level of difficulties they encountered in the use of Blended Learning Modality, this study made use of a self-made data-gathering instrument which was subjected to Validity (4.93 - excellent) and Reliability testing (0.884 for coping strategies and 0.868 for the challenges; both interpreted as "good"). The questionnaire consisted of two parts: Part 1 gathered the respondents' socio-economic information, such as age, civil status, length of service, and highest educational attainment, for the respondents' profile. Part 2 contained the questionnaire proper with 30-line items. There were 15-line items for coping strategies, and 15-line items for the challenges.

Procedure for Data Collection

The researcher sought permission from the Schools Division Superintendent to conduct the study, after which, the Validity and Reliability tests for the instrument was conducted. The approved letter was then distributed to the school heads, where target respondents were assigned. The printed copy of the data-gathering instrument was given to target respondents outside school hours to not distract the Master Teachers and the schools from their routine. The respondents were given three to four days to fill out and return the instrument. Finally, the accomplished data-gathering instrument was encoded and tallied to the pre-formatted Excel file for an orderly tabulation.

Data Analysis and Statistical Treatment

Objective No. 1 used descriptive analytical schemes and mean as statistical tools to determine the level of coping strategies of non-advisory teachers in terms of working environment, ancillary services, and learning modality.

Objective No. 2 also used the descriptive analytical scheme and mean as statistical tool to determine the level of difficulties encountered by non-advisory teachers in the aforesaid areas.

Objective No. 3 used the comparative analytical scheme and Mann-Whitney U Test as statistical tool to determine the significant difference, if any, in the level of coping strategies of non-advisory teachers when grouped according to demographics.

Objective No. 4 used the comparative analytical scheme and Mann-Whitney U Test as statistical tool to determine the significant difference, if any, in the level of difficulties encountered by non-advisory teachers when grouped according to demographics.

Ethical Considerations

The researcher made sure that no personal information that could compromise the identity of the respondents was stored on any device per the Data Privacy Act of 2012, particularly regarding the researcher's and analyst's access to the data. All of the collected data was solely accessible to the researcher. As a result, participants were fully informed about the methods used throughout the research and were urged to sign a consent form to participate.

Participants were also assured that no one, including the public, would learn of the information they disclosed. Furthermore, all materials gathered were disposed of properly. Lastly, participants can voluntarily withdraw from this research study at any time during its duration. A study report would guarantee anonymity.

Results and Discussions

This section presents the data, the analysis, and the interpretation of the same to meet the study's objectives as stated in the objectives. All of these were made possible by adhering to specific protocols that provided precise data and solutions for every objective.

Descriptive Analysis on the Level of Coping Strategies of Non-advisory Teachers According to Selected Constructs

Table 1

Level of coping strategies of non-advisory teachers in the use of Blended Learning Modality in the area of Working Environment

Items	Mean	Interpretation
As a non-advisory teacher, I ...		
1. assist co-teachers with advisory assignments with some classroom activities.	3.80	High Level
2. confer with other teachers to help address classroom issues.	3.95	High Level
3. involve myself in resolving various school issues.	4.00	High Level
4. collaborate with teachers and stakeholders in all school-undertakings.	3.64	High Level
5. join co-teachers in spending off-time outside school premises to unwind.	3.75	High Level
Overall Mean	3.83	High Level

In terms of working environment, the level of coping strategies of non-advisory teachers in the use of blended learning modality is on "high level" as shown in Table 1. This means that the teachers are at ease with their workplace and no massive adjustment is needed.

Item No. 3 which states that "As a non-advisory teacher, I involve myself in resolving various school issues" got the highest mean score of 4.00, interpreted as "high level"; while Item No. 4 which states that "As a non-advisory teacher, I collaborate with teachers and stakeholders in all school-undertakings" got the lowest mean score of 3.64, interpreted as "high level".

The inability of some non-advisory teachers to collaborate or work with co-teachers and some stakeholders could be attributed to their workload and the unavailability of time. Collaboration between teachers and stakeholders (parents, administrators, community members) is essential for creating a supportive and effective learning environment for all students.

Through the lens of social capital, this study examines the significance of collaboration among teachers and their perceived support from school leaders during the first phases of the COVID-19 pandemic. In the study of Sürmeli (2024), showed that teachers who were part of teacher communities or collegial relationships were more likely to get necessary support and cope with the sudden changes. The results imply that schools could better prepare for future disruptions by systematically promoting collaboration within the school and providing teachers with the foundation to establish and build collegial relationships.

Table 2

Level of coping strategies of non-advisory teachers in the use of Blended Learning Modality in the area of Ancillary Services

Items	Mean	Interpretation
As a non-advisory teacher, I ...		
1. take ample time to learn new assignments.	3.55	High Level
2. learn the craft of mastering non-specialized assignments.	3.98	High Level
3. confer with co-teachers on issues I am not familiar with in my new assignment.	3.91	High Level
4. seek guidance from the school head on what to do amidst confusions in my ancillary work.	3.84	High Level
5. maintain an open mind in accepting all other possible assignments the school head deems important.	3.82	High Level
Overall Mean	3.82	High Level

The ability of non-advisory teachers to cope with ancillary services in blended learning showed as “high level” with a mean score of 3.82, as shown in Table 2. This means that the teachers are able to manage all other assigned works apart from his or her specialization.

Item No. 2 which states that “As a non-advisory teacher, I learn the craft of mastering non-specialized assignments” got the highest mean score of 4.98 while Item No. 1 which states that “As a non-advisory teacher, I take ample time to learn new assignments” got the lowest mean score of 3.55, interpreted as “high level”. This implies that most often, taking on a new role such as ancillary assignments is a bit of a stressor particularly on the part where they have to be hands-on without prior training, orientation or in-depth workshop.

Ancestral responsibilities are frequently difficult for Filipino teachers to handle because of their heavy workload and possible administrative overload. These duties may have a detrimental effect on teachers' time management, job happiness, and general well-being. Teachers, however, also exhibit resilience and use a variety of coping strategies, such as setting priorities, managing their time, and asking for help from family and coworkers (Arañas, 2023).

Table 3
Level of coping strategies of non-advisory teachers in the use of Blended Learning Modality in the area of Learning Modality

Items	Mean	Interpretation
As a non-advisory teacher, I ...		
1. keep myself flexible with all kinds of learning modalities available.	3.77	High Level
2. check the internet and co-teachers as to what effective pedagogical strategies shall be used.	3.89	High Level
3. always check each student as to what available resources they have to determine what modality is best for all.	3.86	High Level
4. take time to study each available/applicable modality.	4.05	High Level
5. manage my time well to accommodate any leaning modality the students / parents may want.	3.89	High Level
Overall Mean	3.89	High Level

Table 3 reveals that the ability of non-advisory teachers to cope with whatever learning modality in-place in on “high level” with a mean score of 3.89. This implies that the non-advisory teachers are able to strategically cope with the pressures of shifting from one learning modality to another despite short notices and lead time to prepare.

Item No. 4 which states that “As a non-advisory teacher, I take time to study each available/applicable modality” got the highest mean score of 4.05, interpreted as “high level” while Item No. 1 which states that “As a non-advisory teacher, I keep myself flexible with all kinds of learning modalities available” got the lowest mean score of 3.77, interpreted as “high level”.

This is an indication that despite the resiliency and skills to adapt to new learning modalities, some teachers feel the pressure because of the lack of time to prepare and fully acclimate themselves. To be effective in whatever new learning modality, teachers must be given reasonable amount of time to adjust fully to ensure that they ready to use such modality.

Similarly, Valencia (2024) conducted a study to determine strategies that assisted public elementary school teachers adapt to various changes in their curriculum, particularly with skill-based subjects. The result showed that trainings played a significant role in equipping teachers with the necessary tools to navigate shifts in curriculum structure. The schools that provided structured career enhancement trainings allowed teachers to transition more smoothly, reducing instructional stress and enhancing pedagogical efficiency

Level of difficulties of non-advisory teachers in the use of Blended Learning Modality according to the following areas of Working Environment, Ancillary Services, and Learning Modality

Table 4
Level of difficulties of non-advisory teachers in the use of Blended Learning Modality in the area of Working Environment

Items	Mean	Interpretation
As a non-advisory teacher, I have difficulties ...		
1. with available learning materials.	2.89	Moderate Level
2. in using better instructional strategies due to lack of support.	2.95	Moderate Level

3. with the lack of technical and other support from the school.	3.45	Moderate Level
4. with an overcrowded class/section.	3.04	Moderate Level
5. with the lack of printing materials to produce modules.	3.50	High Level
Overall Mean	3.16	Moderate Level

The difficulties of non-advisory teachers in their working environment during the use of blended learning modality is “moderate”, with a mean score of 3.16, which means that some may be able to cope regularly and well, while others may view such situation as difficult to manage.

Item No. 1 which states that “As non-advisory teacher, I have difficulties with available learning materials” got the lowest mean score of 2.89, interpreted as “moderate level”. Meanwhile, Item No. 5 which states that “As a non-advisory teacher, I have difficulties with the lack of printing materials to produce modules” got the highest mean score of 3.50, interpreted as “high level”. Clearly, at the onset of the implementation of blended learning, teachers were challenged in initially sourcing materials for printing due to some delays in school allocations through the MOOE. The results showed that some teachers find it more than just manageable at their level, but with collegial support, they were able to get through difficult times.

Parallel to this result, a cross-sectional study was conducted by Rajesh (2022) in government, aided, and unaided schools of Udupi, a coastal district in Southern India. A self-administered questionnaire was used to collect the data from 460 high school teachers chosen based on convenience sampling. The coping strategies were identified using a modified version of Brief COPE (Coping Orientation to Problems Experienced) Inventory. The study found that teachers had moderate level of coping skills in all domains. The most popular coping techniques used by secondary school teachers were positive reframing, active coping, and planning; nevertheless, substance use was recognized as the least popular coping strategy. Positive reframing, active coping, and preparation were the most commonly used coping strategies by the teachers in the survey.

Table 5
Level of difficulties of non-advisory teachers in the use of Blended Learning Modality in the area of Ancillary Services

Items	Mean	Interpretation
As a non-advisory teacher, I have difficulties ...		
1. in handling assigned subjects due to lack of training.	2.77	Moderate Level
2. in preparing non-specialized lessons due to lack of time.	3.09	Moderate Level
3. coping with other administrative tasks due to lack of competence.	3.05	Moderate Level
4. with the lack of technical support for the newly assigned subjects.	3.18	Moderate Level
5. In preparing instructional materials for ancillary assignments	3.07	Moderate Level
Overall Mean	3.03	Moderate Level

The difficulties encountered by non-advisory teachers in handling ancillary works during the blended learning was “moderate” with a mean score of 3.03, which means that the extra works being assigned to non-advisory teachers are indeed manageable at their own level.

Item No. 1 which states that “As a non-advisory teacher, I have difficulties with the lack of technical support for the newly assigned subjects” got the lowest mean score of 2.77, interpreted as “moderate level” while Item No. 4 which states that “As a non-advisory teacher, I have difficulties with the lack of technical support for the newly assigned subjects” got the highest mean score of 3.18, interpreted as “moderate degree”.

The result is giving a hint that at the onset of the shift to blended learning, the technical support being provided by the MTs and the academic leaders were not just enough to cover all the technical needs of all teachers. This implies that others were grappling on how to cope although the general view is that the education team was able to successfully implement blended learning despite issues with technical support.

In support of this finding, the result of Sareen (2024) systematic literature review underscored passive learning, design limitations, and deficiencies in training as central challenges in the blended learning domain among the 16 identified barriers. We also develop a 12-factor conceptualization of the term blended learning. Further, our review highlights a significant gap in scholarly research on blended learning barriers emerging from the Humanities and Social Sciences, particularly at the postgraduate level. Additionally, it underscores a lack of multi-stakeholder approaches and cross-disciplinary analyses in the existing literature.

Table 6
Level of difficulties of non-advisory teachers in the use of Blended Learning Modality in the area of Learning Modality

Items	Mean	Interpretation
As a non-advisory teacher, I have difficulties ...		
1. in collaborating with parents.	3.04	Moderate Level
2. with school support as to needed printing materials for self-learning modules.	3.54	High Level
3. finding preferred modality for all as parents are mostly inactive.	2.82	Moderate Level
4. adjusting the common learning time for online learning because some learners have no available parents or guardians.	3.45	Moderate Level
5. In keeping learners' attention during virtual classes as they are easily distracted.	3.18	Moderate Level
Overall Mean	3.20	Moderate Level

The difficulties of non-advisory teachers in the use of blended learning modality were at a "moderate level" with a mean score of 3.20 as shown in Table 8. This is indicative of the fact that the teachers were able to manage issues at their own level with little support from academic leaders in their schools.

Item No. 3 which states that "As a non-advisory teacher, I have difficulties finding preferred modality for all as parents are mostly inactive" got the lowest mean score of 2.82, interpreted as "moderate level" while Item No. 2 which states that "As a non-advisory teacher, I have a difficulty with school support as to needed printing materials for self-learning modules" got the highest mean score of 3.55, interpreted as "high level".

Consistent with the general observations made by other studies, some teachers find themselves in a cumbersome position when printing materials in school were not just enough because they have to put-in their own money at times to purchase coupon bond, inks and other materials for printing purposes. While teachers get a refund later, the urgency to produce needed printing materials might have forced some teachers to look for money somewhere else, if they don't have it on-hand, just to purchase such needs.

Padilla's (2020) study results is aligned with this particular finding. The result of the study showed that novice teachers' challenges in modular distance learning modality are lack of printing materials, and supplies, time consuming, power interruption, parents not getting the modules, schedule not being followed, late submission, unanswered/unfinished modules, and unidentified answer sheets, dirty, damaged modules with torn and missing pages, academic dishonesty and difficulty validating learners' performance. Moreover, proper time management, staying positive and asking advice or guidance from a mentor are the strategies employed by novice teachers in order to cope up with the challenges in modular distance learning modality. In addition, being flexible and knowing how to adapt to changes help them cope up with the challenges encountered.

Comparative Analysis in the level of coping strategies of non-advisory teachers in the use of Blended Learning Modality in the areas of Working Environment, Ancillary Services, and Learning Modality when grouped and compared according to variables Age, Civil Status, Length of Service, and Highest Educational Attainment

Table 7

Difference in the level of coping strategies of non-advisory teachers in the use of Blended Learning Modality in the area of Working Environment when grouped and compared according to variables

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Age	Younger	33	38.06	64.000	0.000		Significant
	Older	23	14.78				
Civil Status	Single	25	41.16	71.000	0.000	0.05	Significant
	Married	31	18.29				
Length of Service	Shorter	32	37.83	85.500	0.000		Significant
	Longer	24	16.06				
Highest Educational Attainment	Lower	35	33.34	198.000	0.004		Significant
	Higher	21	20.43				

Table 7 shows that the p-values for age is 0.00, same with civil status, length of service, and highest educational attainment. All these values are below the 0.05 level of significant, therefore, the interpretation is "significant". The

hypothesis that states there is no significant difference in the level of coping strategies of non-advisory teachers in the use of Blended Learning Modality is hereby "rejected".

This means that age, civil status, length of service and educational attainment significantly affects the level of non-advisory teachers' coping strategies, including their opinion and work-life balance.

In the study of Dela Cruz (2024) the experiences of pre-service teachers in online learning environments were explored, focusing on collaborative learning, technological challenges, coping mechanisms, and time management. Drawing on Moore's Transactional Distance Theory and Bandura's Social Learning Theory, qualitative data from pre-service teachers reveal nuanced insights into their engagement, challenges, and adaptive strategies. Findings underscore the importance of resilience-building interventions and support systems to cultivate a culture of empowerment in online education. Recommendations include integrating resilience-focused pedagogies and mindfulness practices into teacher training programs to enhance educators' capacity to thrive in digital learning environments.

Table 8

Difference in the level of coping strategies of non-advisory teachers in the use of Blended Learning Modality in the area of Ancillary Services when grouped and compared according to variables

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Age	Younger	33	36.23	124.500	0.000	0.05	Significant
	Older	23	17.41				
Civil Status	Single	25	37.16	171.000	0.000	0.05	Significant
	Married	31	21.52				
Length of Service	Shorter	32	38.09	77.000	0.000	0.05	Significant
	Longer	24	15.71				
Highest Educational Attainment	Lower	35	32.50	227.500	0.017	0.05	Significant
	Higher	21	21.83				

Table 8 shows that there is a significant difference in the level of non-advisory teachers' coping strategies in terms of ancillary works with *p*-values for age, civil status and length of service at 0.00; and for highest educational attainment at 0.017, all these values below the significant level of 0.05. Due to this, the hypothesis that says "there is no significant difference in the level of non-advisory teachers' coping strategies" is therefore "rejected".

This implies that age, civil status, length of service, and civil status and length of service affect the coping mechanisms of non-advisory teachers in handling ancillary services.

Salmorin and Motus (2024) investigated the lived experience of teachers in the implementation of blended learning. Seven teachers were selected using purposive sampling and an individual interview was conducted to collect data from the participants. The study illustrated that the main challenges of teachers' experience is lacked of exposure and readiness in the implementation of blended learning; they had experienced mixed reactions towards blended learning modality. They emphasized the struggles in time management, stress from excessive workloads, slow connectivity, and unmotivated students in blended learning instructions. They cope up with the challenges by having more patience and understanding for students who seemed uninterested in blended learning modality, integration of messenger app for educational purposes, adjustment for additional workloads as they eventually become more flexible, and conducting of home visitation for those students who experience internet connectivity issues.

Table 9

Difference in the level of coping strategies of non-advisory teachers in the use of Blended Learning Modality in the area of Learning Modality when grouped and compared according to variables

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Age	Younger	33	34.21	191.000	0.001	0.05	Significant
	Older	23	20.30				
Civil Status	Single	25	37.46	163.500	0.000	0.05	Significant
	Married	31	21.27				
	Shorter	32	33.41				

Length of Service	Longer	24	21.96	229.000	0.017	Significant
	Lower	35	32.46			
	Higher	21	21.90			

Table 9 shows that there is a significant difference in the level of non-advisory teachers coping strategies in managing learning modality. The p-value for age is 0.001, for civil status it is 0.00, for length of service it is 0.008; and for highest educational attainment it is 0.017. All these values are below the 0.05 significant level, thus, the hypothesis that says "there is no significant difference in the level of non-advisory teachers coping strategies" is hereby "rejected".

This implies that the ability of non-advisory teachers to manage, deal and implement learning modalities is affected significantly by their age, civil status, length of service, and educational attainment.

This study of Aguirre (2023) determined the challenges and coping mechanisms of elementary teachers in Blended Learning in Bulan II during the SY 2021-2022. The study employed the descriptive method of research. The respondents of the study were the teachers in Bulan II district. The main instrument that was used in the study is a survey questionnaire which includes the determination of the challenges and coping mechanism of the teachers. The data gathered were analyzed and interpreted by the use of appropriate statistical measures and tools. Based from the data gathered the findings were: This study aimed to determine the challenges and coping mechanisms of elementary teachers in Blended Learning in Bulan II District Division of Sorsogon Province for SY 2021-2022.

Comparative Analysis in the level of difficulties of non-advisory teachers in the use of Blended Learning Modality in the areas of Working Environment, Ancillary Services, and Learning Modality when grouped and compared according to variables Age, Civil Status, Length of Service, and Highest Educational Attainment

Table 10
Difference in the level of difficulties of non-advisory teachers in the use of Blended Learning Modality in the area of Working Environment when grouped and compared according to variables

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Age	Younger	33	19.80	92.500	0.000		Significant
	Older	23	40.98				
Civil Status	Single	25	18.64	141.000	0.000	0.05	Significant
	Married	31	36.45				
Length of Service	Shorter	32	20.77	136.500	0.000		Significant
	Longer	24	38.81				
Highest Educational Attainment	Lower	35	23.70	199.500	0.004		Significant
	Higher	21	36.50				

Table 10 reveals that there is a significant difference in the level of difficulties experienced by non-advisory teachers in managing their working environment. The p-value for age, civil status, and length of service are all on 0.00; and for highest educational attainment, it is 0.004. These values are all below the 0.05 level of significance, therefore, the hypothesis that states "there is no significant difference in the level of difficulties of non-advisory teachers in blended learning" is therefore "rejected".

The result reveals the fact that age, civil status, length of service and highest educational attainment significantly influences the way teachers respond and manage various issues in their work environment.

The study of Fernandez (2023) aimed to determine the teaching-learning challenges and instructional effectiveness encountered in public elementary schools with the use of blended modality. This employed the descriptive survey of quantitative method as participated by 15 public elementary schools with 148 elementary teachers who were selected using purposive sampling procedures. Findings showed that teachers encountered difficulty in anchoring on the learner's assistive technology and learning support needs to the lesson (mean=4.18) and conflict in using a particular learning environment, employing interactive activities and monitoring issue on students' progress with respective mean of 4.06 interpreted as agree. Also, creating positive relationship, setting goals for learners' growth, selecting instructional materials, allowing learners' work independently, and promoting transfer of knowledge were the most

manifested teaching experiences of the teachers. Moreover, blended modality was found effective in teaching outcomes, engagement, and competencies. Furthermore, null hypothesis was rejected at 0.05 level of significance showing that there is a significant relationship between instructional effectiveness of blended modality and respondents' perception on challenges to blended modality and learning experiences.

Table 11

Difference in the level of difficulties of non-advisory teachers in the use of Blended Learning Modality in the area of Ancillary Services when grouped and compared according to variables

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Age	Younger	33	18.17	38.500	0.000		Significant
	Older	23	43.33				
Civil Status	Single	25	15.88	72.000	0.000	0.05	Significant
	Married	31	38.68				
Length of Service	Shorter	32	17.80	41.500	0.000		Significant
	Longer	24	42.77				
Highest Educational Attainment	Lower	35	21.43	120.000	0.000		Significant
	Higher	21	40.29				

Table 11 shows the significant difference in the level of non-advisory teachers' difficulties in dealing with ancillary works in blended learning. The data shows that the *p*-values when grouped according age, civil status, length of service and highest educational attainment were all at 0.00, lower than the 0.05 level of significance, which means that indeed there is a significant difference. The hypothesis which states that 'there is no significant difference in the level of non-advisory teachers' difficulties in blended learning' is therefore "rejected".

This implies that their age, civil status, length of service, and highest education attainment significantly affects their abilities to deal with issues and challenges associated with non-specialized works in the form of ancillary services.

Blended learning in the Philippines is still considered new and young. However, this growing demand for blended learning possesses problems and challenges that are noteworthy to investigate, specifically in emerging higher education institutions, which hinder effective and efficient delivery of teaching and learning. Filipino teachers in blended learning settings have employed various coping mechanisms, including peer sharing and consultation, resourcefulness and innovation in teaching, enhanced monitoring of student performance, and focusing on positive well-being, time management, and openness to change (Ausa, 2023).

Table 12

Difference in the level of difficulties of non-advisory teachers in the use of Blended Learning Modality in the area of Learning Modality when grouped and compared according to variables

Variable	Category	N	Mean Rank	Mann Whitney U	p-value	Sig. level	Interpretation
Age	Younger	33	18.29	42.500	0.000		Significant
	Older	23	43.15				
Civil Status	Single	25	16.48	87.000	0.000	0.05	Significant
	Married	31	38.19				
Length of Service	Shorter	32	17.64	36.500	0.000		Significant
	Longer	24	42.98				
Highest Educational Attainment	Lower	35	23.23	183.000	0.002		Significant
	Higher	21	37.29				

Table 12 reveals that there is a significant difference in the level of difficulties of non-advisory teachers in blended learning in terms of learning modality. The *p*-values for all variables showed a consistent 0.00, except for highest educational attainment which 0.02. All values were below the 0.05 significant level, thus, there exist a significant difference. The hypothesis that states 'there is no significant difference in the level of non-advisory teachers' difficulties in blended learning' is therefore rejected.

This clearly provides information that the skills and competency of non-advisory teachers in dealing with problems related to the chosen learning modality is affected by their age, civil status, length of service and highest educational attainment.

The transition to blended learning environments necessitates a comprehensive understanding of the coping strategies employed by teacher education students. Coping strategies refer to the cognitive and behavioral efforts individuals undertake to manage and overcome stressors or challenging situations. These strategies play a crucial role in determining students' success, satisfaction, and overall well-being in their academic pursuits. In the context of blended learning, teacher education students encounter a range of challenges that require effective coping mechanisms. These challenges may include balancing online and face-to-face learning activities, managing time effectively, navigating digital platforms and tools, and maintaining social connections in virtual environments. The ability of teacher education students to cope with these challenges can significantly impact their academic performance, engagement, and overall learning experience (Castaño, 2022).

Conclusion:

The high level of coping strategies demonstrated by non-advisory teachers is a testament of their dedication to the teaching profession despite some hurdles in adapting with the new teaching and learning trends. Meantime, the moderate level of difficulties encountered by non-advisory teachers in blended learning implies that the issues, situations and other challenges were mostly manageable. There is a significant difference in the level of non-advisory teachers coping strategies showing that age, civil status, length of service and highest educational attainment are significant factors that affect their abilities to cope with many issues relative to Working Environment, Ancillary Services, and Learning Modality. There is a significant difference in the level of difficulties of non-advisory teachers in blended learning. Their ability to address issues and come up on top of every situation is affected by their age, civil status, length of service and educational attainment. Due to the said significant difference, the district leadership may find it difficult to address various difficulties if there is no common ground or unified action to begin with. The significant difference indicates that each group category, example young versus old, single versus married, etc., have different approaches to resolve issues.

Acknowledgment

The completion of this study was made possible through the collaboration and encouragement of the following individuals: Dr. Lilybeth P. Eslabon, Dr. Rey T. Eslabon, and some colleagues. Thank you for your assistance.

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